

Circle packing inside a regular pentadecagon: supplemental material

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular pentadecagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular pentadecagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular pentadecagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceed by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is large:

configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular pentadecagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.493133395003	0.500880509957	41	0.135827391017	0.778993589345
3	0.459339047264	0.651873452267	42	0.134285460356	0.77997841536
4	0.40699739034	0.682367839122	43	0.132839943452	0.781449880414
5	0.367155419957	0.69413701044	44	0.131715241216	0.786140279763
6	0.330869393637	0.67645630779	45	0.130375566772	0.787735181109
7	0.327244319326	0.772000500703	46	0.128952850181	0.787762008491
8	0.297701136798	0.730173861943	47	0.127640470924	0.788587634797
9	0.272092054641	0.686198144012	48	0.126519330668	0.791280235469
10	0.258769830772	0.689608479493	49	0.125056825729	0.789198391249
11	0.250987901042	0.713630770631	50	0.123991417245	0.791641516155
12	0.24525331258	0.743337973628	51	0.12290758624	0.793419490706
13	0.233258591424	0.728440290891	52	0.121794550867	0.794391099258
14	0.227740446201	0.747796932723	53	0.120503931642	0.792599168547
15	0.218419147385	0.736966901512	54	0.120070134376	0.801750173405
16	0.213488734913	0.751009134615	55	0.119472197189	0.808484504217
17	0.205729279778	0.740996987108	56	0.117745046689	0.799555525381
18	0.202255567522	0.758313495633	57	0.116766332686	0.800360129559
19	0.201730511417	0.796291517388	58	0.115783042154	0.800743119322
20	0.192381611411	0.762311411889	59	0.114583872107	0.797763770333
21	0.187632715972	0.761398004197	60	0.113822408038	0.800538270174
22	0.181362657703	0.74523584	61	0.113292327933	0.806317611899
23	0.178174367236	0.751958019964	62	0.111729082845	0.797075511259
24	0.175473627788	0.761044866536	63	0.110972872243	0.799005028137
25	0.17250007783	0.766114899704	64	0.110074809882	0.798603430467
26	0.170298665874	0.776553083877	65	0.109402395827	0.801202566182
27	0.16836201467	0.788183431979	66	0.108567616588	0.801161096765
28	0.163697719154	0.772713673461	67	0.107721103757	0.80066658035
29	0.160868818668	0.772888868575	68	0.107231405542	0.805245338126
30	0.158917906374	0.780265193149	69	0.106847825844	0.811251997408
31	0.155977032566	0.776708951916	70	0.105712318593	0.805609439021
32	0.153127899757	0.772740971486	71	0.104994421775	0.80605766172
33	0.151794657144	0.783072946675	72	0.104148153549	0.804286826144
34	0.149404813236	0.781597936871	73	0.103390170665	0.803630986363
35	0.147126416009	0.780233629268	74	0.102656989611	0.803126725662
36	0.145963846257	0.789893259438	75	0.102036522432	0.804170005099
37	0.145167710374	0.803002851658	76	0.101438387223	0.805366522842
38	0.141559726544	0.784220762184	77	0.100836206996	0.806304413005
39	0.139698271055	0.783830175627	78	0.100098613708	0.80487055151
40	0.138277813782	0.7876627545	79	0.09958499301	0.806845154307

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular pentadecagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0991287395207	0.809588749188	121	0.0810294314766	0.818175109502
81	0.0987324708396	0.813168111727	122	0.0806605834525	0.817443713527
82	0.0983480662542	0.816809559763	123	0.0802940234033	0.816670487103
83	0.0977059089936	0.816009210393	124	0.0799573330761	0.8164199239
84	0.0971718665668	0.816837534311	125	0.0796025705102	0.815716987334
85	0.0966493232681	0.817695993878	126	0.0794025459203	0.818115667418
86	0.095747028087	0.811940801392	127	0.0791371646838	0.819105803594
87	0.0951331704253	0.810883573381	128	0.0788155033778	0.818857981131
88	0.0945410763673	0.810026200642	129	0.0784808526426	0.818262116904
89	0.09400543051	0.809974229408	130	0.0781605245267	0.817887540144
90	0.093555772565	0.811258009665	131	0.0779004056266	0.818702361537
91	0.0929036323136	0.808876261457	132	0.0776183724572	0.818989444728
92	0.0923665375731	0.808337012405	133	0.0774133166093	0.820839597778
93	0.0918923847443	0.808755602984	134	0.0771644467357	0.821702486311
94	0.0914585860131	0.809752184724	135	0.0769655657577	0.823572829024
95	0.0910796807966	0.811599768406	136	0.0766763050007	0.823448741635
96	0.0905884964017	0.811320864785	137	0.0764851573902	0.825372901203
97	0.0902104444723	0.812944110083	138	0.0761624028752	0.824395609867
98	0.0899036590351	0.81574819291	139	0.0757757086641	0.821958939018
99	0.0896449530483	0.8193362921	140	0.0753997526342	0.819677826968
100	0.0889280390738	0.814428084253	141	0.0751637823611	0.820373597409
101	0.0884610761168	0.813956357342	142	0.0749346760686	0.821162904673
102	0.0882238973369	0.817613322165	143	0.0746323009616	0.820285452669
103	0.0875089947476	0.81230275084	144	0.0744141873929	0.821200657942
104	0.0871849897168	0.814126872354	145	0.0741336728293	0.820680937133
105	0.0868456463367	0.815569003842	146	0.0738913978395	0.820948530744
106	0.086404428358	0.814991683835	147	0.073690160045	0.822075383263
107	0.0859100238327	0.813292497613	148	0.0734695571734	0.822719648044
108	0.085460130902	0.812318178567	149	0.0732558491361	0.823466984104
109	0.0851219248952	0.813363499613	150	0.0730997238292	0.82546381597
110	0.0847859115037	0.814358026942	151	0.0728355648603	0.824972063348
111	0.0844962618752	0.816156193026	152	0.0726260501152	0.825664756828
112	0.084256294825	0.818838108127	153	0.0724593631864	0.827286173449
113	0.0838875572802	0.818933900673	154	0.0722389271394	0.827634536285
114	0.0835984465928	0.820496203361	155	0.0719975316055	0.82745087934
115	0.0833415299998	0.822613983652	156	0.0717535957296	0.827155661262
116	0.082990711657	0.822796197698	157	0.0715147215545	0.826924512391
117	0.0825992679277	0.822079025049	158	0.0712911888693	0.826997336191
118	0.0822797207101	0.822702722314	159	0.0710157125841	0.825812271313
119	0.0818729291049	0.821491221555	160	0.0707398534262	0.824562544559
120	0.081446766208	0.819793077287	161	0.0705327331555	0.824864497328

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular pentadecagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.070234917227	0.822993630008	182	0.0664555476791	0.827769042563
163	0.0700921938151	0.824711822054	183	0.0662561142506	0.827329143748
164	0.0698096534533	0.823095299632	184	0.0661340432903	0.828787673134
165	0.0696216342158	0.823659439388	185	0.0659541373195	0.828764473626
166	0.0695171337854	0.826165609525	186	0.0658198001658	0.829853389894
167	0.0693038236567	0.826049691176	187	0.0656710725673	0.8305487611
168	0.0692007510875	0.82852612576	188	0.065455440994	0.829515804659
169	0.0689270971797	0.826879055685	189	0.065335478875	0.830874194471
170	0.0686759270555	0.825720928177	190	0.0652546686293	0.833205422252
171	0.0685783501785	0.828219564813	191	0.0650779118157	0.833059257249
172	0.068403415509	0.828818299004	192	0.0648842911827	0.832445226571
173	0.0682773871605	0.830568007997	193	0.064683272401	0.831604029201
174	0.068138051061	0.831962923571	194	0.0646071435408	0.833946364033
175	0.0680050790951	0.833481679512	195	0.0644520101055	0.834224333736
176	0.06773219816	0.8315307571	196	0.0642297677446	0.832729756599
177	0.0675364262218	0.831428154816	197	0.0641198533058	0.834116237807
178	0.067332592469	0.831086033582	198	0.0639753381694	0.83457559368
179	0.0670624747402	0.829062920239	199	0.0637823071032	0.833736537487
180	0.066848785235	0.828390012077	200	0.0636379692603	0.834138045448
181	0.0667530670669	0.830608428614			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular pentadecagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

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References

- [1] Amore, Paolo. "Circle packing in regular polygons." arXiv preprint arXiv:2212.12287 (2022).
- [2] Paolo Amore, "Coordinates of the packing configurations of arXiv:2212.12287 ", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574070>